

Deliverable D4.2

Microbiological traceability tools using target and non-target metagenomics and initial map of origin defining genetic markers

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Document Type		
PRO	Technical/economic progress report (internal work package reports indicating work status)	
DEL	Technical reports identified as deliverables in the Description of Work	X
MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
MAN	Procedures and user manuals	
WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a Technical report	
INF	Information and Notes	

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
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1. Executive Summary

The main goal of the WP4 is to develop of a suite of tools for metagenomic, genetic and stable isotope approaches to determine quality, safety and traceability of FishEUTrust seafood products within the supply chain. In this report, contribution to Deliverable 4.2 are reported, comprehending:

TO4.1: Definition of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for sampling, DNA extraction and processing of samples for NGS based metagenomics (responsible: UNIFI)

TO4.1.1: Microbiological traceability tools using target and non-target metagenomics (responsible: UNIFI)

TO4.1.2: Initial map of origin defining genetic markers (responsible: UNIPD)

It is also related to MS6, MS7 and MS8. The main goal is to integrate the data obtained from metagenomics, as proposed by the Task O4.3 in validated SOP protocols, in identified use-cases. This will be also implemented for the development of an alternative methodology to certify fish authenticity, origin based and freshness. In this report, results obtained during the achieving process are reported.

2. T04.1: Definition of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for sampling, DNA extraction and processing of samples for NGS based metagenomics (responsible: UNIFI)

Genomic DNA extraction and amplification from fish cloacal swab and gills biopsy protocol

Equipment needed:

Sterile swabs 15 x 0,5 x 0,5 cm

RNA Later (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific)

DNeasy Powersoil Pro Kit (QIAGEN)

PCR BIO Classic Taq (PCR ByoSystems, London)

Notes

Before starting sampling, measure the fish in weight and length. If possible, do the sampling under BSC to prevent contamination of the swab and rinse the fish around cloacal opening with ethanol 70% to prevent skin microbiota contamination of the swab. Prepare 2mL tubes with 1,5 mL of RNA Later (or at the least to completely cover the head of the swab).

A) Sampling Procedure

Cloacal swab

Insert the head of the swab in the fish cloaca for about 2 cm (depending on the fish size). Rotate the swab several times.

Cut the head of the swab and put it in the 2 mL tube with RNA Later. Be sure that all the swab is fully immersed in the solution.

Store the sample at – 20 °C.

Gills

Using sterile scissors or other cutting instruments, perform a biopsy of about 3 cm of gills (both cartilage and lamellar tissue) on one side of the fish (always the same side).

Put the biopsy in a 2 mL tube with RNA Later. Be sure that all the sample is fully immersed in the solution.

Store the sample at – 20 °C.

B) Genomic DNA Extraction

Extract genomic DNA from swabs using DNeasy Powersoil Pro Kit (QIAGEN), according to the manufacturer's instructions (attached).

Equipment needed for DNeasy Powersoil Pro Kit

Microcentrifuge (up to 16,000 x g)

Pipettor (50–1000 µl)

Vortex-Genie® 2 (or other vortex agitators)

Vortex Adapter for 24 (1.5–2 ml) tubes (cat. no. 13000-VI-24)

Extracted gDNA could be stored:

- at RT for 1 week

- at 4°C for one month
- at -20°C for long term storage

C) Amplification of gDNA

Prepare a PCR mix using PCR BIO Classic Taq (PCR ByoSystems, London) using the following protocol:

Buffer	5 µL
Primer F	0.5 µL
Primer R	0.5 µL
H ₂ O	16.75 – 17.75 µL
Taq	0.25 µL
DNA	1 – 2 µL
Total volume	25 µL

For Illumina targeted sequencing, use the following primer:

- 16S V3-V4
 - o 341F (5' – TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGCAGCCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG – 3')
 - o 805R (5' – GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTCTACNVGGGTWTCTAATCC – 3')
- ITS1
 - o ITS1F (5' – TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGGGTCAATTTAGAGGAAGTA – 3')
 - o ITS1R (5' – GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGGCTGCGTTCTTCATCGATGC – 3')

For amplification, use the following PCR Cycles:

16S V3-V4			ITS1		
95° C	3 min	1 cycle	95° C	3 min	1 cycle
95° C	30 sec	30 cycles	95° C	20 sec	35 cycles
55° C	30 sec		50° C	45 sec	
72° C	30 sec		72° C	90 sec	
72° C	5 min	1 cycle	72° C	10 min	1 cycle
4° C	∞	1 cycle	4° C	∞	1 cycle

Check PCR products on an 1.5% agarose nucleic acid-stained gel

- Amplicons must be stored at -20°C

Protocol of genomic DNA extraction from clams

Equipment needed:

- Sterile blade
- Sterile petri dish
- Stomacher bags
- Stomacher

- DNeasy Powersoil Pro Kit (QIAGEN)
- Sterile Eppendorf 1,5 ml
- Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (Sigma-Aldrich)

NOTE: Work in sterile conditions (use of microbiological hood) according to the type of analysis to be performed

Sampling dissections and extraction:

- 1- Cut the adductor muscle of the clam with a sterile blade and open the valves.
- 2- Remove the total body of the animal and the extra-pallial liquid and collect into a sterile petri dish (collect three clams per sample)
- 3- Transfer the sampled clams to a stomacher bag and weigh them
- 4- Add a quantity of PBS equal to the weight of the sample per 9
- 5- Homogenize the sample with the Stomacher instrument for 1 min at maximum speed
- 6- Transfer the filtered sample into a new tube (1,5 ml) and centrifuge for 5 min at maximum speed
- 7- Discard the supernatant and suspend the pellet in the lysis buffer provided by the kit (use the quantity indicated in the kit protocol)
- 8- Transfer the sample suspended in the lysis buffer in the PowerBead Pro Tubes (provided by the kit)
- 9- Bead beating can be carried out using a standard benchtop vortex or using TissueLyser (1 min for 30 hertz)
- 10- Centrifuge the PowerBead Pro Tubes at 15000 rpm for 1 min, then follow the DNeasy Powersoil Pro kit manufacturer's instructions
- 11- Store the sample at -20°C

Tissue isolation for animal genetic analysis

FISH

Clip the fish anal fin and store in absolute (or 95%) Ethanol solution

CLAM

Cut a small piece of clam mantle and store in absolute (or 95%) Ethanol solution

3. TO4.1.1: Microbiological traceability tools using target and non-target metagenomics (responsible: UNIFI)

3.1 Traceability

In this section, data already reported in MS8 are expanded with the new data available obtained from sequencing of samples sent by Living Labs. In fact, the first results obtained are inescapable, from a technical, technological and methodological point of view, for the subsequent analysis of the samples obtained, and they also go to form an integral part of the Standard Operating Procedures. Sequencing of samples from the living labs was possible using the methodology implemented with the first local samples described the results of which are published in a full paper (Meriggi et al., 2024)

In order to advance tasks 4.1 “*Developing a Metagenomics Sequencing Toolbox for determining the origin, of seafood products, and test protocols for determining freshness, pathogens, and antibiotic resistance*” and 4.3 “*Developing a Metagenomics Sequencing Toolbox for determining the origin, of seafood products, and test protocols for determining freshness, pathogens, and antibiotic resistance*” we first set an experiment to test our protocol and at the same time obtaining the first dataset about microbial communities associated to two fish species of commercial interest, *Dicentrarchus labrax* (seabass) and *Sparus aurata* (seabream).

In the first part of the project, we collected local samples from the Tuscan Coast by a local company (Cooperativa San Leopoldo, Tuscany, Italy) that provided the whole fish frozen. First data revealed that gills are more informative than cloacal swabs (in addition, gills microbiota is not affected by diet, but by host-microbe factors and environmental factors, which is more likely to meet our needs). We collected gill tissues from 10 *Dicentrarchus labrax* (seabass) and 10 *Sparus aurata* (seabream) from 3 different sampling sites (60 specimens total) located at very limited distance one from another, to check the validity of the method at a limited geographical distance.

After the arrival of samples from the other project partners, samples from Spain, Croatia, Malta, and Portugal were integrated into the analyses.

Genomic DNA was extracted from gills tissue by DNeasy Powersoil Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), according to manufacturer instructions. The genomic DNA was visualized for quality and integrity on stained agarose gel and quantified using Qubit 4 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA USA) 1x dsDNA High Sensitivity kit. For each sample, PCR amplification of 16S V3-V4 hypervariable regions was performed, using primers 341f and 805r.

Sequences obtained by Illumina MiSeq sequencing were processed using the following computational approaches.

The sequences of the forward and reverse primers were removed by cutadapt. If the primer sequence was not identified, the entire sequence was discarded to reduce possible contamination. The raw sequences were processed using the DADA2 pipeline version 1.26 to produce amplicon sequence variants (ASVs). The quality of the sequences

was first inspected by selecting the first two sequenced samples as forward and reverse to assess the parameter setting of the sequence filtering and cutting step (Figure 1).

Sequence filtering and cutting was then performed using the 'filterAndTrim' function, filtering out low-quality sequences with a maximum number of expected error thresholds of 2 for direct and reverse read pairs and a sequence cut length of 280 and 220 base pairs for forward and reverse sequences, respectively. We performed error rate estimation via the 'learnErrors' function (Figure 2) and denoising via the 'dada' function with default parameters.

Denoise reads were merged using the 'mergePairs' function, discarding those with possible mismatches. Chimeric sequences were removed using the 'removeBimeraDenovo' function and taxonomic classification was produced using the DECIPHER package version 2.26.0 against the pre-formatted Silva reference database (Quast et al., 2012) (SSU version 138 available at: <http://www2.decipher.codes/Downloads.html>). All sequence variants not assigned to the Bacteria domain, i.e. unknown or assigned to chloroplast and mitochondria sequences, were removed from the dataset to perform the subsequent statistical analysis correctly. Statistical analyses were performed in the R environment version 4.2.2. Beta diversity was explored by using the "vegan" package version 2.6.4. Rarefaction curves were calculated and depicted by using the "ggrare" function of "ranacapa" package version 0.1. Core microbiome was assessed by using the "microbiome" package version 1.20. After removal of single counts and transformation into relative abundances, the distribution of samples was visualised by Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) using the "cmdscale" function of the "stat" package based on Bray-Curtis distance index. Permutational multivariate analysis of variance using distance matrices (adonis permanova) was performed to inspect differences between sample groups using the "adonis2" function of the "vegan" package version 2.6.4. Pairwise comparisons on variance among different sites were assessed using pairwise adonis permanova by using the "pairwise.adonis" function from "pairwiseAdonis" package version 0.4. Alpha diversity measures were produced by the "estimate_richness" function from the "phyloseq" package version 1.42 while Evenness was defined as the index/log of Shannon diversity (observed richness). Significant differences among groups were assessed by using the Wilcoxon pairwise test using the "wilcox_test" function from the "rstatix" package version 0.7.2. Abundance-occupancy analysis was performed to detect core membership among fishing sites. Core microbiota were assessed on compositional-transformed abundances by using the "plot_core" function of "microbiome" package version 1.20.

Differential abundance analysis was performed using the likelihood ratio test (LRT) implemented in the DESeq2 package version 1.38.3. Before the LRT test, singletons were removed to mitigate the hypothesis that extremely rare species could be considered the main drivers of differences between the groups. The size factor estimate was calculated using the "postcount" method to estimate geometric means of ASVs in the presence of zeros using the "estimateSizeFactors" function of the "DESeq2" package. ASVs abundance values depicted in the ternary space were calculated using the "microbiomeutilities" package version 1.0.17 with default parameters (abundant threshold = 0.0001, prevalence threshold = 0.1) then displayed by using "ggtern" package version 3.4.2. The figures were produced using the "ggplot2" package version 3.4.2 and edited

using the open source graphics editor Inkscape 1.1.2 (<http://inkscape.org/>). Beta diversity analysis represented by Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) based on the Bray-curtis distance index shows clear differences in the distribution of samples from the different catch areas in the two different fish species (Figure 1). In particular, about the species *Sparus aurata* (gilthead seabream), a marked separation was evident between the Livorno (Li) site and the other two sites, Cecina and Grosseto (Ce, Gr), which showed a greater overlap between them (Figure 1). Using the multivariate permutation analysis based on distance matrix (adonis permanova) performed using the 'adonis2' function of the 'vegan' package, the effect of the site variable was assessed. The analysis shows that the site variable significantly affects bacterial gill diversity in both species (R² in Figure 1). In addition, sequence variants clustering shows a strong clustering of samples according to their sampling site for seabass (Figure 2), while for seabream clustering was present but less strong (not reported).

Figure 1. Multidimensional scaling analysis (PCoA) based on Bray-Curtis distance according to the main two variables, fish species (shape pattern) and site (color pattern). R-squared values and significance after adonis permanova analysis tested on species and site variables are reported inside the panel. (b-c) PCoA based on Bray-Curtis distance performed after splitting the dataset according to the fish species, i.e. seabream (b) and seabass (c). PCoA reported sample distribution according to the different sites (color pattern) while R-squared values and significance from adonis permanova analysis are reported on top of the panels. (d) Heatmaps display statistical significance and R-squared values from pairwise adonis permanova for each comparison between groups, from lower value (blue scale) to higher value (red scale). Significant pairs are reported using asterisks (ns; not significant, *; P<0.05, **; P<0.01)

Figure 2. Sequence variants clustering across different fishing sites in seabream dataset. ASVs that significantly vary within fishing sites (LRT of DESeq2) are clustered according to their variance-stabilized abundance (VST scaled abundance). ASVs clustering is produced according to Ward D2 method and rows/columns branches are built using Euclidean distance. ASVs scaled abundance values are reported using color gradients reported in the legend. ASVs are reported on the heatmap rows while samples are reported on the columns

Our analysis suggested the presence of an association among fishing sites and specific taxonomic features. Ternary plot (Figure 3) shows the ASVs relative abundance distribution, with taxonomic references associated to each sampling site with statistical significance.

These results confirm the validity of our proposed methodology to assess the traceability of fish using gills microbial communities, demonstrating the possibility of discriminating between fish species and sampling sites (even if they are located at a very limited geographical distance). Gills, in addition, are very easy to obtain, they can be easily collected from fish, and the procedure does not alter appearance and organoleptic qualities of the fish.

Figure 4. Boxplots of bacterial diversities across different sampling sites and indices

Bacterial communities' composition showed deep differences between sampling sites, but differences were also observed between wild and cultured fishes. Among the same sampling site, dominant genera were found to be consistent across samples. However, the dominant genera were not the same in different sampling sites (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Barplot of the most abundant bacterial genera among all samples

NMDS analysis showed that differences between wild specimens are lower than the differences between cultured fishes. However, a clear distinction between Italian and non-Italian samples is visible. Concerning cultured specimens, all the sampling sites resulted to be distinct from each other, with a partial overlap between samples from Malta and Portugal (Figure 6).

Figure 6. NMDS plots of samples from wild fishes (left) and fishes from aquaculture (right) built using Bray-Curtis distance. Color of points represents the sampling site

Differential abundance (DA) test was conducted on both ASVs and genera, in order to detect significantly different distributions across sampling sites. As seen in the barplot (Figure 5), bacterial communities from cultured fishes presented a more stable and less diverse communities, and this was reflected in the DA results. Indeed, for the aquaculture group less ASVs were significantly more or less abundant across all sites. From the cluster analysis of ASVs, four clusters were identified: cluster 1, mainly abundant in Spain; cluster 2, abundant in Croatia and, even if less, in Malta; cluster 3, most abundant in Malta and Portugal; cluster 4, mainly abundant in Malta. By looking at the classification at the genus level (Figure 7) it is interesting that cluster 2 is mostly composed of ASVs from the genus *Shewanella*.

Cluster analysis of samples was able to distinguish sampling sites with a high accuracy and a low number of outliers.

Figure 7. Heatmap of scaled and centered relative abundances of ASVs from cultured fishes with a significant p-value (<0.05) in the DA analysis. On the top of the heatmap is shown the dendrogram produced with the cluster analysis of samples. Rows represent ASVs. On the right of the heatmap are the barplots of the log10 ASVs abundances and their cluster analysis dendrogram. Colors of barplots and samples' dendrogram represent the sampling site, colors of the dendrogram on the right represent the clusters retrieved

For wild fishes, *Shewanella* resulted again to be highly associated with Malta samples together with *Acinetobacter*. Instead, *Psychrobacter* was significantly linked to Italian samples. Also in this case, four AVSs clusters were identified, of which two of them (clusters 3 and 4) highly linked to the Italian site, while cluster 1 being more abundant in Malta, and cluster 3 in Portugal and Spain (Figure 4).

For wild fishes, *Shewanella* resulted again to be highly associated with Malta samples together with *Acinetobacter*. Instead, *Psychrobacter* was significantly linked to Italian samples. Also in this case, four AVSs clusters were identified, of which two of them (clusters 3 and 4) highly linked to the Italian site, while cluster 1 being more abundant in Malta, and cluster 3 in Portugal and Spain (Figure 4).

Figure 8. Heatmap of scaled and centered relative abundances of ASVs from wild fishes with a significant p -value (<0.05) in the DA analysis. On the top of the heatmap is shown the dendrogram produced with the cluster analysis of samples. Rows represent ASVs. On the right of the heatmap are the barplots of the \log_{10} ASVs abundances and their cluster analysis dendrogram. Colors of barplots and samples' dendrogram represent the sampling site, colors of the dendrogram on the right represent the clusters retrieved

Results of the differential abundance were then filtered to identify a short set of bacterial markers which could discriminate with a high accuracy the different sampling sites.

To allow the model to run in the presence of zeroes, an artificial taxon was added (called "BASE" in Figure 9 and Figure 10) with relative abundance values randomly sampled between 0.1 and 0.11 and randomly distributed across the samples. For both wild and aquaculture samples, the procedure of randomly assign abundances to the BASE was run multiple times to ensure it was not influencing the cluster analysis. For both the datasets the dendrogram produced by the cluster analysis resulted extremely stable.

For aquaculture samples, were identified 7 markers: one for Spain, one for Croatia, one for Portugal and four for Malta.

For wild samples, 8 markers were found: One for Portugal, two for Italy, and five for Malta. No specific marker was identified for Spain.

Figure 9. Heatmap and cluster analysis of site-specific bacterial markers for aquaculture samples. Tip point colors represent the sampling site, the color of the heatmap cells shows ASVs' scaled and centered abundance

Figure 10. Heatmap and cluster analysis of site-specific bacterial markers for wild samples. Tip point colors represent the sampling site, the color of the heatmap cells shows ASVs' scaled and centered abundance

In addition to this work, we performed a similar methodology to a wider set of samples from 22 sampling sites across the Mediterranean. From each of these sampling sites, samples of seawater and *Mullus barbatus* (mullet), another important fish species. In this case, we had access to a limited number of samples for each sampling site (3 specimens),

but the sampling sites covered a very wide area along the Mediterranean Sea. In this case, we used gut tissue. Specimens were collected from local fishermen, and gut were immediately extracted with sterile forceps and preserved in RNALater. Extraction of gDNA, sequencing and statistical analysis were performed as mentioned. The main results of this work were: 1) gut microbiota is more simplified and less informative compared to gills microbiota. 2) Clustering of samples anyway works even at a higher spatial resolution.

Indeed, mullet's gut microbiota showed to be composed at the ~98% of two single genera (i.e., *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*, Figure 6, left), hence showing an extremely low diversity (Figure 11, right). However, by removing the two dominant genera, cluster analysis revealed that rare species can be useful to detect geographical differentiation of fishes' microbiota. Indeed, results obtained from cluster analysis showed that samples taken from geographical locations close to each other also had the lowest inter-sample variability (Figure 12, left). Three main clusters of samples were obtained: a Mediterranean one, one for the Black Sea and the northern Aegean Sea, and one for the southern Aegean Sea (Figure 12, right). The division in these 3 clusters was tested with the PERMANOVA analysis. Results confirmed that this division in clusters explain the 23% of microbial communities' composition variability ($R^2 = 0.23$), with a p-value of 0.027(*).

Results obtained from this set of samples highlighted the possibility to assess fishes' origin from their gut microbiome, although, according to this results, gut microbiome seems to be less informative compared to gills microbiota.

Figure 11. Barplot of the 10 most abundant genera (left); boxplot of Shannon diversity indices (right)

Figure 12. Heatmap and cluster analysis of bacterial ASVs (left); geographical distribution of clustered samples (right)

3.2 Freshness

To evaluate microbial communities related to freshness, we set up an experiment using the protocol developed for traceability experiment. We collected individuals by a local wholesaler of *S. aurata* and *D. labrax*, we simulated supply chain/consumer conditions, storing whole fish at 4°C, and we collected every day for three days a gill sample from each fish. In addition, we performed everyday simultaneously to the sampling the *Quality Index Method* (QIM) (Table 1), assigning a spoilage score to each fish at the exact time of sampling, to correlate specific microbial signatures to specific spoilage states.

Table 1. *Quality Index Method (QIM) Table, developed and adapted by Larsen et al. (1992)*

Quality parameter	Character	Score (ice/seawater)
General Appearance	Skin	0 Bright, Shining
		1 Bright
		2 Dull
	Bloodspot on gill cover	0 None
		1 Small, 10-30%
		2 Big, 30-50%
		3 Very Big, 50-100%
	Stiffness	0 Stiff, in rigor mortis
		1 Elastic
		2 Firm
		3 Soft
	Belly	0 Firm
		1 Belly burst
	Smell	0 Fresh, seaweed/metallic
		1 Neutral
		2 Musty/sour
		3 Stale meat/rancid
Eyes	Clarity	0 Clear
		1 Cloudy
	Shape	0 Normal
		1 Plain
		2 Sunken
Gills	Colour	0 Characteristic, red
		1 Faded, discolored
		2 Swaty/slightly rancid
	Smell	0 Fresh, seaweed/metallic
		1 Neutral
		2 Sour stink/stale rancid
		3 Sour stink/stale rancid
Sum of scores		(Min. 0 and Max. 20)

For the analysis of samples, we followed the same protocol described above. We collected two kinds of samples for each individual: a gill biopsy and a gill swab (obtained by swabbing the whole gill). This was done to assess if there are any relevant differences between the two sampling methods and to select the easiest but effective method. The methodology used for sequencing is the same as depicted above for the traceability experiment. Quality of sequencing is reported in Figure 13, to demonstrate the good quality of sampling and sequencing. Statistical analyses are currently being performed. Preliminary results are depicted in Figure 14, showing a bar plot of the main bacterial genera associated with seabass and seabream, for both sampling matrices. This early data shows that swabs and gill biopsies give similar results. If this will be confirmed, gill swabbing, for the easier obtaining method, could be proposed as a standard method of sampling fish specimens. Currently, the same samples were shipped to University of Padova that are replicating the sequencing, to test the repeatability of the method. Microbial biodiversity serves as a crucial indicator of freshness. In our experiments, a diverse microbial population often indicates freshness, as spoilage microbes have not yet dominated. In our case-study, the gills of *Digentrarchus labrax* and *Sparus aurata*, show rich microbial communities after fishing denote freshness and quality, whereas a reduction in biodiversity is sign of signals spoilage, or longer shelf-life.

Figure 13. Quality profiles of forward and reverse reads. The panels in the figure show the quality profiles of the readings of the first two samples, for forward and reverse sequences. The top two panels represent readings from forward sequences and the bottom two

Figure 14. Relative abundances at Genus level. The bar graphs represent the main taxonomic classes associated with the gills and the gill swabs of sea bass and sea bream. Taxonomic assignments at the genus level are shown in the legend following the color code

Microbial data from gills' swabs were used to investigate spoilage-related microbial changes.

All of the used indices showed that the spoilage process influences deeply the microbial community composition. As also shown in Figure 5, there is a complete dominance of a few taxa over the others, with the passing of time, resulting in a fast decrease in diversity values (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Diversity indices change with spoilage. The boxplots show the values (y axis) of 7 different diversity indices at the three time points (x axis)

To determine which ASVs were statistically increasing or decreasing over-time, we performed a differential abundance analysis. This method found 42 ASVs which decrease and 19 ASVs which increase in abundance with fish spoilage (Figure 16).

Taxonomical allocation of the two groups of ASVs was done at the genus level. The group showing a significant decrease at the timepoint 2 was mainly composed of the genera *Shewanella*, *Psychrobacter*, *Flavobacterium*, *Candidatus Branchiomonas*, and *Bizonia*. The ASVs which took advantage of fish spoilage were assigned to the genera *Photobacterium*, *Shewanella*, *Moritella*, *Cetobacterium*, and *Aliivibrio* (Figure 17). Most of the latter genera (*Photobacterium*, *Shewanella*, *Moritella*) are already identified as spoilage-specific organisms (Boziaris & Parlapani, 2017).

Interestingly, ASVs belonging to genus *Shewanella* were found both increasing and decreasing over-time. This is probably due to the fact that they belong to two different species, and at this moment of the analysis they cannot be distinguished.

Figure 16. ASVs which are influenced by fish spoilage. Volcano plot showing the ASVs (represented by points) which decrease and increase in abundance over-time. In blue the ASVs which significantly decrease between time 0 and 2, in red the one increasing

Figure 17. ASVs abundances change over-time. Barplots showing the abundance of the differentially distributed ASVs along the three time points. On the x axis are represented the samples, on the y axis the relative abundance of the ASVs. The plots are split horizontally based on the trend (on top the ASVs decreasing with spoilage, on the bottom the ones increasing) and vertically based on the time point

3.3 Biolog EcoPlate Approach

To increase the tools at our disposal, with a view to increasing the simplicity and cost-effectiveness of microbiota-based methods, and to flank the sequencing-based method we also tried to implement a methodology that did not involve a sequencing step, using a microbial ecology approach through the Biolog EcoPlate Assay. The Biolog EcoPlate assay is proposed as a new approach to assess the traceability of seafood products, offering advantages in terms of technical simplification over other molecular techniques for microbial profiling. The EcoPlate assay, known for its high-throughput capabilities in microbial ecology, has been employed to assess the functional diversity of microbial communities derived from various fisheries organs and origins.

The EcoPlate Biolog assays involves a 96-well microplate containing a set of 31 carbon sources and one control repeated three times. Measuring the utilization of these carbon sources, differences in the microbial communities of different samples can be assessed. We focused on *Sparus aurata* (sea bream), with the goal of discriminating between aquaculture-reared and wild-caught individuals in the Mediterranean area.

To distinguish between wild-caught and farmed fish, we used samples taken from the anterior and posterior intestines, cloaca swabs, and gills. The gills revealed accurate clustering of sample origin, particularly through color development at 47 hours for carbon sources such as α -cyclodextrin, D-cellobiose, glycogen and α -D-lactose. Cloaca, anterior and posterior intestines did not prove to be appropriate candidates for analysis. To further

validate the effectiveness of our method, we conducted a simulated experiment, successfully identifying the origin of an anonymous sample by principal component analysis (PCA). Shannon and Simpson's indices were also used to statistically assess EcoPlate diversity, reflecting the clustering of different organic samples.

Initially, phenotypic differences were observed between wild and reared sea bream from anterior and posterior intestines, cloaca, and gills. During the 48-hour incubation period, all selected metabolites showed increased in colour development. Among the four organ sections examined, the anterior and posterior intestine samples were excluded from the analysis. This decision was made based on the high variability observed in the technical replicates due to difficulties in achieving the correct dilutions. In addition, the presence of intestinal contents could not be reliably predicted because full and empty intestines were sampled during the experiment. From a technical point of view, sampling the anterior and posterior intestines also involved complex dissection procedures, whereas access to the gills and cloaca was much easier, especially for purposes for industrial monitoring purposes. Consequently, the analysis focused on the gill and cloaca samples, which proved to be reliable sources.

Figure 18. The utilization of selected carbon sources by microbial communities from both wild-caught and farmed specimens was assessed in cloaca (A) and gills (B), across three distinct time frames. Horizontal bars represent Kruskal-Wallis test, error bars represent standard errors. If error bars are not visible, it is because the size of the symbol (or box) is bigger than the error bars. **** $p < 0.001$; *** 0.0002; ** 0.0021; * 0.0332; ns, not significant. (adapted by Nerini et al., 2024)

Next, an in-depth analysis of the gill and cloacal microbiota was carried out. For this purpose, three time points were chosen that showed the most significant differences, namely at 4 h, 24 h and 47 h of incubation. Several metabolites, including, β D,L- α -Glycerol Phosphate, D-Cellobiose, Glucose-1- Phosphate, Glycogen, i-Erythritol, L-Phenylalanine, L-Threonine, Tween 80, α -Cyclodextrin, α -D-Lactose and β -Methyl-D-Glucoside, were selected as the most promising metabolites to be monitored. The results of our experiments showed no differences in between wild and reared sea bream when cloaca was tested (Figure 18). However, when we repeated the experiment on the gills, significant differences were observed for all selected metabolites at both 24 and 47 hours (Figure 18). In addition, when comparing the microbial communities obtained from the gills in terms of arbitrary Omnilog units at 47 hours, we found significant differences between reared and wild sea bream for the following metabolites: β -methyl-D-glucoside, α -cyclodextrin, glycogen, D-cellobiose, glucose-1-phosphate and α -D-lactose.

To evaluate the possibility of discriminate traceability using Biolog, data obtained of different metabolites at different time points depicted in Figure 18 were used to conduct a mock experiment. An unidentified resuspension of gills/cloaca was given to the operator, and a PCA analysis was performed. Results show a separation of samples according to fish origin (wild/farmed). Separation was corroborated by the R-squared values (reported in Figure 19), obtained from multivariate analysis (adonis PERMANOVA). The mock community (wild-caught specimens), clustered in accordance with fish origin, aligning with wild-samples.

Figure 19. Differences in substrate consumption profiles in samples from different fish origins. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) based on Euclidean distance reporting samples from different fish origins (color scheme). Fish tissue (gills or cloaca) and related time point (T0, T24 and T48) are reported at the top of each panel. R-squared (R2) values and significant effect of origin variable, tested with adonis PERMANOVA, are given in square brackets at the top of each panel. A significant effect is indicated with asterisks (*** $p < 0.001$)

Concluding, PCA analysis demonstrated the possibility of discriminate production method of fishes, also reinforcing the suggestion that gills could better distinguish between farmed and wild specimens, as already suggested.

3.4 Untargeted Sequencing

To improve the depth of sequencing of samples, an untargeted metagenomic sequencing was performed. Samples from both spoilage experiment and tracking experiment were sequenced, for a total of 48 samples

Previously extracted gDNA was mechanically sheared through sonication using an M220 Focused-Ultrasonicator. Fragmented DNA was checked for quality through Fragment Analyzer System (Agilent Technologies). DNA libraries were prepared using a Kapa HyperPlus Kit (Roche Sequencing, Pleasanton, CA), and paired-end sequenced (2 x 150 bp), on an Illumina NovaSeq6000 with dual indexing into a single sequencing run.

Raw base calls data demultiplexing was performed using Illumina Conversion Software bcl2tofastq v2.0. Adapters and primer pairs sequences were removed by using *cutadapt* version 3.5 and *sickle* Sequences were aligned references genomes (*Sparus aurata*, *Dicentrarchus labrax*) using *bowtie*.

Figure 20. Read counts resulting from sequence processing. Each bar represents the number of sequences resulting after each step of reads processing (reported in x-axis). Unaligned sequences represent the sequences that were not aligned to reference genomes (*Sparus aurata* and *Dicentrarchus labrax*)

Samples were selected to improve the depth of taxonomical resolution and to detect ARGs and SSOs. In this perspective, a set of samples were selected from those already available to us. Samples from spoilage experiment were all sequenced (excluding T1

samples, that were deemed unnecessary for our research question). Samples obtained by swab sampling method were used, in an optic to simplify the sampling and making it affordable and time-effective for anyone in the supply chain, without visually and qualitatively altering the product. Regarding tracking experiment, a statistical approach was used to select the most informative samples. Using the algorithm *k-means*, the cluster center of each sample was statistically identified. Samples mathematically closest to the cluster (identified by previous targeted sequencing) were selected for untargeted sequencing. The primary results of sequence processing are reported in Fig. 20.

4. TO4.1.2: Initial map of origin defining genetic markers (responsible UNIPD)

Knowledge of population structure and genetic diversity within and between wild and farmed populations of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) is an important tool for traceability of commercialized fish. Taking advantage of the completely sequenced sea bream genome (Pauletto et al., 2018) a SNPs array was recently developed for this species based on about 25k SNPs (Penaloza et al., 2021). The performance of this SNPs array was tested on 27 farmed and wild populations from numerous locations throughout the species range (Fig. 21). It was tested the ability of the array to distinguish/identify the population on a genetic base.

Figure 21. Map of sampling locations for wild seabream in dark blue (from Villanueva et al., 2022)

Population structure revealed a clear differentiation between wild and farmed populations in both species. Wild populations showed a low degree of differentiation. Despite this, a slight differentiation was observed between Atlantic and Mediterranean seabream populations and between western and eastern Mediterranean. Farmed populations were quite heterogeneous and showed a high degree of differentiation. Thus, this array was demonstrated to be effective at detecting population structure across a

wide range of fish populations from diverse geographical origins, and to examine the extent of haplotype sharing among Mediterranean farmed fish populations (Villanueva et al., 2022).

Within the FishEUTrust, we used the SNPs array described above on a sample set of wild and aquacultured sea bream obtained from Spain (CATEGA), Portugal (IPMA) and Malta (AquaBioTech). The purpose was to verify the ability of this genetic tool to differentiate the three populations sampled in the FishEUTrust project and identify the origin of each fish sample. The other goal was to test the possibility to assign back each fish to its population of origin.

From the three sites we obtained 30 individuals catch in the wild and 30 from local sea bream farms. In the case of Spain, the samples from cultivated fish were only 20. (Fig. 22)

Samples

Figure 22. Sampling site of wild and aquacultured sea bream. In each box is reported the sample size and the reference code: S_A=Spain aquaculture, S_W=Spain wild, P_A=Portugal aquaculture, P_W=Portugal wild, M_A=Malta aquaculture, M_W=Malta wild

Samples collection and DNA extraction

For each fish specimen we received a little piece of gill (few grams) preserved in etOH 90% which allowed shipment at ambient temperature. Sample were collected at different dates and registered in a database accessible to the involved partners at the following link:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1HzdRnQ4iXVpigJZymM0vrNCB3_pW8cJCWG_NW1eXo-pQ/edit?pli=1&gid=0#gid=0

DNA Extraction was carried out as follow: Individual gill samples from *Sparus aurata* preserved in ethanol were stored at -20°C until laboratory analysis. DNA extraction was

performed using the Invisorb® Spin Tissue Kit (Invitex, © STRATEC Molecular), following the manufacturer's protocol. The quality of the extracted DNA was assessed through gel electrophoresis on a 1% agarose gel. DNA concentration and purity were measured using a NanoDrop ND-1000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The DNA samples were then sent to IdentiGEN Ltd for further analysis.

After some difficulty in finding the company for the SNPs array analysis (due to increased prices of the usual provider), we finally got a convenient agreement with *Benchmark Genetics* (<https://www.bmkgenetics.com/>) that processed our 170 DNA samples. SNPs profiles were provided on September 5 and analyzed to verify: 1) the genetic differentiation of the 6 populations (3 wild and 3 cultivated), 2) the possibility to assign fish samples to their population of origin. Of the 170 DNA processed for SNPs profiling 9 of these did not reach the quality necessary for a reliable signal (M_A_19, M_A_25, M_A_26, P_W_21, P_W_22, P_W_24, P_W_25, P_W_26, S_A_9), therefore they were excluded and the analyses were referred to 161 individual SNP profile based on 27,913 common SNPs.

Population structure

The first goal was to verify the existence of some genetic cluster among the 161 samples of *S. aurata* we applied a *Discriminant Analysis of Principal Components* (DAPC) by using *Adegenet 2.1.6* . (Jonbart and Collins, 2022). The results are reported in the graphic representation of Fig. 23. The SNPs profiles clearly distinguish the 6 sample groups (S_A, S_W, P_A, P_W, M_A, M_W) in 6 distinct clusters providing evidence of the ability of this genetic tool to discriminate groups.

Figure 23. DPCA on 161 sea bream sample based on 27,913 common SNPs

Interestingly, the wild and aquacultured Spanish samples cluster close each other indicating a high degree of genetic affinity. This is not the case of Portuguese and Malta samples possibility because the brood stock of these two implants obtained their breeders from different geographic origins.

Population assignment

The second goal was to test the possibility to assign with a certain probability an individual to its population/group of origin. To this end, we used the “AssignPOP” bioinformatic tool (Chen et al., 2018) that helps to perform population assignment using a machine-learning framework. It generates a SNPs reference baseline and then assign “unknown” samples (that were not part of the dataset used to generate the baseline) to one population with a certain probability.

Details of AssignPOP procedure are reported hereafter.

AssignPOP is an R package that helps perform population assignment using a machine-learning framework. It employs supervised machine-learning methods to evaluate the discriminatory power of data collected from source populations, and is able to analyze large genetic, non-genetic, or integrated (genetic plus non-genetic) data sets. The ability to assign individuals of unknown origins to source populations relies on a robust baseline (or training data) collected from the source populations.

Evaluate baseline data

The baseline data are individuals and their genetic features (SNPs individual profile) collected from known or source populations and it is important to evaluate this data via cross-validation before using it to predict source populations of unknown individuals.

To analyze genetic data, the package provides the function *read.Genepop* that allows users to import a GENEPOP format file into R. The function converts genetic data to a numeric format, following the method used in ADEGENET where each allele is encoded as 0 (absent), 0.5 (heterozygote) or 1 (homozygote). To reduce dimensionality in the training dataset, which is useful when there are a large number of markers a PCA analysis step is always conducted on molecular data. Our baseline consists of a dataset of 149 individuals from the 6 populations/groups (S_A, S_W, P_A, P_W, M_A, M_W) since 12 individuals (3 per each group) were excluded from baseline creation and used as “unknown” for posterior population assignment (see below). To evaluate the baseline we tested 3 different classification machine-learning functions to build the predictive models (SVM, randomForest and naiveBayes).

Perform resampling cross-validation

To estimate membership probability a *K*-fold cross validation was used, in which individuals from each population are divided into *K* groups. One of the *K* groups is tested by the predictive model built based on the remaining *K*-1 groups. We divided individuals from each population into 6 groups (or folds). After the resampling cross-validations analysis, we calculated the assignment accuracies for the three machine learning models tested. The SVM model resulted with the best accuracy value. After baseline data were evaluated through resampling cross-validation and the assignment results were satisfactory, we used the entire baseline data to build a predictive model and perform assignment tests on individuals of unknown origins to predict their source population.

Our unknown individuals (not included in the baseline dataset) were: M_A_1, M_A_9, M_A_27, M_W_1, M_W_6, M_W_18, P_A_1, P_A_11, P_A_27, P_W_1, P_W_14, P_W_29, S_A_1, S_A_14, S_A_24, S_W_1, S_W_8, S_W_15

Predict sources of unknown individuals

The function *assign.X* provides the predicted source population of each individual and its posterior probability of membership to that population, as well as the others.

The assignment functions use PCA for dimensionality reduction. It converts independent variables to Principle Components and retain the PCs that have eigenvalues greater than 1 (the Kaiser-Guttman criterion) as new features.

The result of individual assignment to one the identified populations and the associated posterior probability is reported in Fig. 24.

Figure 24. Assignment of “unknown” individuals to one population and associate posterior probability

All M_A, M_W, P_A and S_A individuals were correctly assigned to their origin population with 100% probability, whereas, individuals P_W_1, S_W_1 and S_W_8 were miss-assigned. The possibility of using the larger dataset including the populations described in Villeneuve et al. (2022) for generating a wider baseline will be explored.

5. Impact

Two full papers were published in international peer-reviewed journals

- Meriggi, N., Russo, A., Renzi, S., Cerasuolo, B., Nerini, M., Ugolini, A., ... & Cavalieri, D. (2024). Enhancing seafood traceability: tracking the origin of seabass and seabream from the tuscan coast area by the analysis of the gill bacterial communities. *Animal Microbiome*, 6(1), 13.
- Nerini, M., Russo, A., Decorosi, F., Meriggi, N., Viti, C., Cavalieri, D., & Marvasi, M. (2024). A Microbial Phenomics Approach to Determine Metabolic Signatures to Enhance Seabream *Sparus aurata* Traceability, Differentiating between Wild-Caught and

Farmed. Foods, 13(17), 2726.

Two research article and one review are being prepared along with UNIPD and JSI.

Dissemination

Results of research were presented (or are going to be presented) at national and international conferences.

- Russo. A, D' Alessandro A., Meriggi, N., Nerini, M, Cerasuolo, B., Renzi S., Ugolini A., Marvasi M., Cavalieri D. *TRACEABILITY AND FRESHNESS OF SEAFOOD ASSESSING THROUGH MICROBIAL COMMUNITIES: PROPOSING A TARGETED METAGENOMIC APPROACH*. In 53th Congress Società Italiana di Biologia Marina, Rome 12-13th June 2024 (**AWARD WINNING POSTER**)
- Russo A., Nerini M., D'Alessandro A., Meriggi N., Cerasuolo B., Renzi S., Ugolini A., Patarnello A., Maritino M.E., Marvasi M., Cavalieri D. *16S rRNA TARGETED METAGENOMIC SEQUENCING TO ASSESS SEAFOOD TRACEABILITY AND FRESHNESS*. In 83th Unione Zoologica Italiana, Pisa, 11th-14th September 2024
- One other poster is going to be presented at IUMS 2024 (International Microbiological Societies Congress, 23th-25th October 2024)

6. Conclusions

Results obtained during the advancement of D4.2 (*Microbiological traceability tools using target and non-target metagenomics and initial map of origin defining genetic markers*) are very promising. Targeted sequencing has been shown to be able to discriminate different sampling sites (and thus fish product origin) based primarily on cluster analysis. With this approach it was also possible to find site-specific bacterial markers, as already demonstrated by analysing the first set of local samples, the results of which have already been published in a full paper. Untargeted sequencing, whose protocols have been refined and adapted for extraction and fragmentation of genomic DNA from fish gills, has been successfully carried out and currently the data are being analysed. This will allow us to improve the depth of information obtained, as well as obtain data regarding Antibiotic Resistance Genes (ARGs) and Specific Spoilage Organisms (SSOs). The alternative phenotypical approach proposed, namely Biolog Ecoplate, could be an alternative or go alongside sequencing-based approaches, increasing the tools available for determining the provenance and quality of the catch in a food safety and security optic. The overall picture suggests that the results obtained in these 27 months of the project are solid and consistent with the goals of the FishEU Trust project. The next step will focus on method validation. Following the collection of new samples by Living Labs, in fact, we could compare new data with those already available to us, assessing the method's reproducibility and degree of accuracy even at different time points

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